

Synthesis and Structural Characterisation of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3,5-dinitrobenzoylhydrazone Complexes

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Polymerisation reactions involving the formation of bipoisitive metal complexes of Schiff bases are reported. Schiff base acts as a tridentate ligand and oxo-bridged binuclear dimeric species is formed which is confirmed with the aid of analytical, magnetic, thermal, ir and dr spectral studies. The metal ion is the bridging unit between the donor sites of the ligand, and the polymeric chain grows through consecutive ligand-metal linkages.

METAL complexes^{1,2} of Schiff base derived from hydrazides and aldehydes or ketones are of potential biochemical importance in the context of their therapeutic value³. The coordination may occur either through the ketonic or the enolic oxygen^{3,4,5} and the carbonyl group plays a significant role in the chelation. Larsen⁶ studied the molecular structure of dimeric Schiff base complexes and interpreted the results by molecular exciton theory based on the measurement of absorption and CD spectra. Formation of oxygen-bridged bi- and tri-nuclear complexes have been described in several reviews⁷⁻⁹. Metal complexes of Schiff bases obtained from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with amines and oxalyhydrazide with diacetyl have been isolated by Poddar and Saha¹⁰. These multinuclear oxygen-bridged complexes have offered interest in synthesising a variety of isomeric compounds and sometimes contain mixture of monomeric and oxygen-bridged dimeric species^{11,12}. Mention may also be made of the work reported from these laboratories on Schiff base complexes¹³⁻¹⁷.

The present paper describes the synthesis of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3,5-dinitrobenzoylhydrazone and their characterisation by analytical, magnetic, thermal and infrared and diffuse reflectance spectral data.

Experimental

3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka, AG), hydrazine hydrate (AnalaR), methanol (HPC), ethanol (BC), DMF (Sisco) and metal acetates (AnalaR), were used.

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3,5-dinitrobenzoylhydrazone (NBHZ): The hydrazide (0.01 mol) in

acetone (20 cm³) was gradually added to 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.01 mol) in acetone (20 cm³). The mixture was refluxed for ~30 min and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with hot acetone and dried over CaCl₂ (80%), m.p. 240°.

Metal complexes: The metal salt (0.002 mol) dissolved in DMF-aqueous medium was added to the hydrazone (0.002 mol). The mixture was refluxed on a sand bath for 2-4 h as required in different cases. The Cu^{II} complex was obtained almost instantaneously whereas Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were obtained after the addition of a few drops of ammonia. The precipitates of metal complexes were filtered, washed with hot DMF and dried. The complexes are coloured polycrystalline solids, insoluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, DMF and DMSO.

Results and Discussion

The microanalytical data (Table 1) of the complexes suggest the general formula ML₂.2H₂O, where M(II)=Mn, Co, Ni or Cu; and H₂L=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3,5-dinitrobenzoylhydrazone (C₁₈H₁₂N₄O₆) abbreviated as NBHZ

The ir spectra of the ligand showed bands at 2 870, 3 210, 1 725, 1 670, 1 570, 1 530, 1 312 and 1 015 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{O-H} , ν_{NH} , $\nu_{C=O}$, ν_{C-N} , $\nu_{ONH} + \delta_{NH}$, ν_{C-O} , ν_{OH} and ν_{N-N} , respectively. The important observations made by ir spectral analysis of all the metal complexes are the disappearance of bands (cm⁻¹) at (i) 3 210 due to NH stretch, (ii) 1 725 due to C=O stretch, (iii) 1 570 due to $\nu_{ONH} + \delta_{NH}$; and appearance of new bands at (iv)

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd*.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	Diffuse spectral band cm ⁻¹		Ligand field parameters	
	M	N					
MnL.2H ₂ O	11.02 (11.73)	11.08 (11.96)	4.70	⁶ A _{1g}	19 231 → ⁴ T _{1g} (G) 21 739 → ⁴ T _{2g} (G) 22 988 → ⁴ E _g (G) → ⁴ B _{1g} (G) 25 641 → ⁴ T _{2g} (D) 28 571 → ⁴ E _g (D) 30 303	10Dq B	10 680 854
CoL.2H ₂ O	12.85 (12.46)	11.90 (11.81)	3.60	⁴ T _{1g} (F)	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (F) 10 204 → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) 21 744 → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) 22 727	10Dq B β β° ν ₁ /ν ₂	11 540 924 0 951 4.85 2 12
NiL.2H ₂ O	12.30 (12.45)	11.01 (11.84)	2.76	⁸ A _{2g} (F)	→ T _{2g} (F) 10 869 → ⁸ T _{1g} (F) 17 544 → ⁸ T _{1g} (P) 29 412	10Dq B β β° ν ₁ /ν ₂	10 869 963 0 912 8.56 1.62
CuL.2H ₂ O	12.89 (13.19)	11.30 (11.72)	1.42	² B _{1g}	→ ² A _{1g} 10 638 → ² B _{2g} 11 364 → ² E _g 16 667	10Dq σ ₁ /σ ₂	12 109 1 46

*Ligand H₂L (C₁₀H₈N₄O₆) Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.) C, 55.92 (56.85) ; H, 3.07 (3.16) ; N, 14.20 (14.73).

1 665–1 645 due to $\nu_{O-O-N} + \nu_{O-N}$ and (ν) 1 600–1 595 attributed to C=N–N=C¹⁸ stretch. The appearance of these bands suggest the enolisation of the ligand in the solution while in the solid state it exists in the keto form (1, 2) since no significant positive shift in ν_{O-O} (phenolic) band at 1 530 cm⁻¹ is noticed ; it rules out the possibility that coordination occurs via phenolic oxygen bridges^{7, 10, 19-21}. An enolic oxygen bridge is likely to exist as suggested.

The ν_{O-N} at 1 670 cm⁻¹ shifts to lower frequency indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in the complex formation. There are two C=N₂

stretching frequencies due to difference in environment, one is coordinated and the other non-coordinated. The disappearance of OH stretching at 2 870 and OH deformation at 1 312 cm⁻¹ suggest the participation of phenolic oxygen in the metal complexes under study. The positive shift of the ν_{N-N} from 1 015 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand to 1 030–1 045 cm⁻¹ on complexation with a metal ion indicates the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in bonding. Since this shift is less than 50 cm⁻¹, it further emphasises that only one of the azomethine nitrogen is involved²². A new stretching band appears at 770–80 cm⁻¹ attributed to

via phenolic oxygen than keto oxygen⁸. A similar band has been observed by Griffith²³ in the range 710–90 cm⁻¹ due to oxobridged skeleton in dimeric complexes. Two additional bands are noticed at 455–75 and 415–20 cm⁻¹ in the metal-sensitive region and are tentatively assigned to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} modes, respectively²¹.

Another band observed at 1 570 cm⁻¹ may be a composite band due to $\nu_{OH} + \delta_{NH}$ and ν_{-N} , which shifts to higher frequency by 25–35 cm⁻¹ indicating the formation of binuclear species. Other important characteristics of binuclear complex formation are the appearance of new bands of high intensity around 1 190 and 1 240–1 248 cm⁻¹ and disappearance of a band near 1 205 cm⁻¹ found in the mononuclear complexes^{8, 24}. The shifting of ν_{O-O} to higher frequency side is also indicative for the binuclear structure.

The presence of water molecule within the coordination sphere in the complexes is confirmed by the presence of respective bands at 3 600–3 500, 1 635–1 630 and 975–965 cm^{-1} due to OH stretching, deformation and rocking modes of coordinated water. This is confirmed by TG data where percentage weight-loss occurs at 195–225° corresponding to the elimination of two water molecules. The complexes decompose at 260–400° and the order of thermal stability is $\text{Co} > \text{Mn} \approx \text{Ni} > \text{Cu}$.

All the complexes are paramagnetic as shown by their anomalous low magnetic moment values (Table 1). At room temperature μ_{eff} is typically 1.42 B.M. per Cu atom identical to those observed for carboxylate-bridged $\text{Cu}_2(\text{OCOCH}_3)_4 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and ascribed as antiferromagnetic couplings of the unpaired species on the adjacent Cu^{2+} atoms. Similarly, the μ_{eff} values of the other metal complexes are lower than expected for octahedral complexes indicating significant M–M interactions and support their binuclear dimeric structure^{6,7-9}.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes show appropriate transition corresponding to various bipositive cations. In the case of octahedral Co^{2+} complex, the ${}^4A_{1g}$ level is close to the ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) level and transition to these levels are also close together as shown by their band positions (21 744, 22 727 cm^{-1}). The Cu^{2+} complexes appear brown in colour which may be due to one of the strong d–d transition band tailing off into the blue end of the visible spectrum. Ligand field parameters, viz. $10Dq$ or Δ_o , B' , β , β^0 , and the ratio of transition ν_2/ν_1 (or σ_1/σ_2 in the case of Cu) have been calculated (Table 1) which are in agreement with the octahedral geometry of the complexes. However, the study of magnetic moment with varying temperature, X-ray analysis and esr studies may prove to be more helpful for the confirmation of the structure.

In the light of above discussion, the ligand NBHZ acts as tridentate coordinating through azomethine nitrogen, enolic oxygen and phenolic oxygen of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and an oxygen-bridged dimeric structure may be tentatively assigned²⁵⁻³⁰ (3).

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